

REVIEW

Benchmarking metabarcode sequence denoisers for improved invertebrate community diversity estimates

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Abstract

1. DNA metabarcoding is fast becoming a method of choice for the inventory and monitoring of community-level arthropod biodiversity, with growing interest in the recovery of haplotype-level variation within species from metabarcoding reads. Denoising tools have been established as the standard for metabarcode processing, with the promise to provide accurate sequence data at the haplotype level.
2. Despite their widespread use, the accuracy of denoising methods relative to the elimination of non-target sequences and retention of target sequences has received limited attention. Recent studies based on whole organism community DNA (wocDNA) metabarcoding suggest that misleading estimates of species richness and diversity may be obtained after denoising. Understanding and evaluating how denoising pipelines perform and how they can be improved is crucial for broadening the applicability of metabarcoding to community ecology, metaphylogeography and biodiversity inventory and monitoring.
3. To evaluate the performance of the most popularly used denoising tools, we use (i) complex communities from malaise traps subjected to wocDNA metabarcoding (representing the information yielded by metabarcoding) and (ii) additional sequencing of each individual specimen (representing the ground truth of sample contents). To these data, we apply the metabarcoding evaluation rationale described in Andújar et al. (2021), complemented by an additional layer of clustering and filtering with LULU and metaMATE.
4. This study confirms that denoising tools alone, but also in combination with clustering, retain a high number of non-target amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) and operational taxonomic units (OTUs). Both LULU and metaMATE removed large amounts of non-target sequences and noise. This, however, came at the cost of the collateral removal of target sequences. We recommend a workflow including one of the better performing denoising tools: DADA2 or UNOISE3, in combination with LULU or metaMATE as a customizable option for evaluating pipeline performance.

KEYWORDS

arthropod, barcode, clustering, denoising, metabarcoding, NUMT, taxonomic inflation

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1 | INTRODUCTION

DNA metabarcoding is fast becoming a method of choice for the inventory and monitoring of community-level arthropod biodiversity (Arribas et al., 2022; Kennedy et al., 2020), with growing interest in the recovery of haplotype-level variation within species from metabarcoding reads (Andújar et al., 2022; Serrana & Watanabe, 2021; Shum & Palumbi, 2021). However, the accuracy and reliability of both species-level and haplotype-level inferences from metabarcoding reads have received limited attention. Uneven PCR amplification success and variation in size and abundance across species can manifest themselves as the underestimation of both the true species composition within a community sample and the haplotype-level variation within species (Elbrecht et al., 2017). Similarly, PCR and sequencing error may generate reads that are minor variations of target sequences, potentially resulting in the overestimation of haplotype variation within species (Coissac et al., 2012; Macé et al., 2022; Zinger et al., 2019). Artificial sequences formed during PCR by the incorrect joining of DNA fragments, so-called ‘chimeras’, are a further source of error (Bjørnsgaard Aas et al., 2016), and sample contamination may also result in false inferences about community composition (Bohmann et al., 2021). Finally, the co-amplification of nuclear copies of mtDNA (NUMTs) can lead to erroneous inflation of both overall species composition and intraspecific haplotype variation (Andújar et al., 2021). Together with typically limited reference libraries for many taxonomic groups and the potential for erroneous taxonomic annotation of publicly available reference sequences, NUMTs can be difficult to distinguish from authentic mitochondrial amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) (Keck et al., 2022; van der Loos & Nijland, 2020). This has been demonstrated to produce substantial overestimation of species richness within arthropod community samples (Andújar et al., 2021).

Uneven PCR amplification success, as well as size and abundance variation across species, can potentially be addressed by improved primer design (Andújar et al., 2018) and size sorting prior to DNA extraction and amplification (Elbrecht et al., 2021). However, issues of contamination are likely to be project-specific and dependent upon field and laboratory protocols (Ficetola et al., 2016; Zinger et al., 2019). For the removal of chimeras, there are many effective tools (Callahan et al., 2016; Edgar et al., 2011). More challenging are the universal issues of avoiding sequence variants arising from (i) errors in the PCR and sequencing processes and (ii) the co-amplification of NUMTs. All of these processes may result in sequence variation that is consistent with expectations for functional mtDNA variation, but is not of a direct origin from mtDNA (Cihlar et al., 2020; Strobl et al., 2019). To further enhance the robustness of metabarcoding data and reduce spurious ASVs and low-frequency noise, independent sample replication from the extraction stage onward—retaining only ASVs consistently detected across replicates—has proven effective (Buchner et al., 2024). This consensus-filtering approach adds minimal cost while significantly improving the accuracy of

taxon detection by reducing technical artefacts. Incorporating such replication strategies contributes to a higher signal-to-noise ratio and more reliable ecological inferences.

To address erroneous sequences more broadly, the most common approach remains the use of clustering, denoising or a combination of both (Brandt et al., 2021; Nugent et al., 2021), which are implemented in what we refer to as primary denoisers. While both approaches are frequently used, we lack a general understanding of their performance and suitability for different combinations of data characteristics (i.e. different marker genes and organisms) and analytical goals, such as phylogenetic reconstruction or population genetics (Creedy et al., 2021). The core of many clustering approaches is to cluster reads based on an arbitrary sequence identity criterion, typically from 97 to 99% sequence similarity (Bombin et al., 2020; Xiong & Zhan, 2018), such that only the most abundant sequence in the cluster is retained. This reduces the number of erroneous sequences but also results in the loss of haplotype-level resolution below the clustering threshold. Such loss precludes the extension of metabarcoding to the analysis of variation within species (Bonin et al., 2022). Alternative approaches, considering relative read abundances (e.g., UNOISE3; Edgar, 2016) and read quality through the application of an error model to reduce sequence and PCR errors (e.g. DADA2; Callahan et al., 2016), have been proposed as denoising methods. However, these approaches do not specifically address NUMTs.

A wider exploration of the presence of noise, including NUMTs, and its removal by abundance-based filtering approaches has recently been addressed with the program metaMATE (metabarcoding Multiple Abundance Threshold Evaluator; Andújar et al., 2021), which can be considered as a secondary denoiser. It can process the output of various primary denoisers, such as DADA2 or UNOISE3, which generate amplicon sequence variants (ASVs). While other primary denoisers may produce different output formats with different terminology, including zero-radius operational taxonomic units (ZOTUs; Edgar, 2016; Antich et al., 2022), ESV (exact sequence variant), sOTU (sub-OTU) or ISV (individual sequence variant), we will for simplicity refer to all of these collectively as ASVs. MetaMATE classifies a subset of ASVs and subsequently filters and evaluates ASV retention using a range of user-defined thresholds on ASV abundance (Andújar et al., 2021). To classify ASVs, they are queried against reference sequences (either on public databases, local reference libraries or both), so that exact matches are classified as verified authentic ASVs (vaASVs). A subset of NUMTs/erroneous ASVs is also identified with metaMATE through the presence of stop codons or insertions and deletions (indels), which are classified as verified non-authentic ASVs (vnaASVs). A range of user-defined thresholds can then be explored to estimate the proportion of surviving sequences after filtering with regard to the known numbers of: (i) authentic ASVs, i.e. sequences that accurately represent a target sequence from the mitochondrial genome and (ii) non-authentic ASVs (i.e. NUMTs/erroneous ASVs). Thus, metaMATE provides a framework to identify thresholds that optimize across the two

desired outcomes from the bioinformatic processing of metabarcoding sequencing output: the retention of authentic ASVs and the removal of non-authentic ASVs. Such optima may vary according to individual research project needs. For example, if one is interested in quantifying spatial patterns of genetic variation within species, it may be desirable to choose thresholds that minimize the retention of non-authentic ASVs, even at the cost of removing authentic ASVs. Alternatively, if one is interested in estimating local species richness and diversity, thresholds penalizing the loss of authentic ASVs may be less desirable—but only as long as the estimation of species richness is not inflated. In addition to metaMATE, LULU (Frøslev et al., 2017) also functions as a secondary denoiser. It examines the co-occurrence patterns of ASVs across samples, based on which it merges ASVs that appear to be erroneous with their correct counterpart.

A range of denoising approaches is now available for metabarcoding data; however, validation approaches to understand their performance are lacking. In response to this, we evaluate the performance of the three most prominent denoising tools that are applied to arthropod whole organism community DNA (wocDNA) metabarcoding data: DADA2 (Divisive Amplicon Denoising Algorithm; Callahan et al., 2016), UNOISE3 (Edgar, 2016) and DnoisE (Antich et al., 2022). In addition, we also assess the effectiveness of SWARM (Mahé et al., 2014), a routinely employed single-linkage clustering tool. With the exception of DnoisE, the initial development and testing of tools being evaluated here have been in the context of the analysis of ribosomal sequences (Antich et al., 2022). The application of these tools to other markers, such as the animal barcode region (658bp section of the mtDNA cytochrome oxidase I [COI] gene), is frequently accompanied by a lack of detail regarding both parameter settings (e.g. OMEGA_A for DADA2, α for UNOISE3 and DnoisE, d for SWARM) and the underlying reasoning (Creedy et al., 2021), suggesting that default parameters may have been carelessly applied without consideration (Antich et al., 2022). This practice is potentially problematic, as genetic variation and evolutionary properties can differ significantly across different genetic loci. Thus, a deeper understanding of parameter setting and their consequences is needed.

Our overarching objective is to take a mock community type approach to compare the performance of the primary metabarcoding denoising programs UNOISE3, DADA2, DnoisE and SWARM, and the secondary denoisers LULU and metaMATE when applied to COI metabarcoding data generated from arthropod wocDNA. As the barcode region of the mtDNA COI gene is recognized as the marker of choice for the metabarcoding of arthropod communities (Andújar et al., 2018), we use it as the focal marker for our benchmarking exercise. We use a set of 45 arthropod community samples from Malaise traps across Sweden ($n=44$) and Finland ($n=1$). This included more than 36,000 specimens that were pooled by sample for bulk DNA extraction and metabarcoding sequencing, after which each specimen was individually barcode sequenced. Thus, our results provide a foundation for denoising decision making for researchers engaged in wocDNA metabarcoding.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Data generation

2.1.1 | Sampling

The present study leverages a comprehensive dataset generated by Orsholm et al. (2025), which consists of a total of 45 samples collected from Malaise traps across Sweden and Finland. The number of collected individuals per sample varied between 36 and 3228 (averaging 793 ± 750). Locations and sampling details are provided in Orsholm et al. (2025).

2.1.2 | Generation of reference barcode sequences

Barcode reference libraries provide the opportunity to validate metabarcoding reads and evaluate the performance of alternative metabarcoding processing pipelines. Public reference databases often lack complete information, limiting the conclusions that can be drawn from them. To circumvent this issue, we have developed a near complete local reference library. The malaise samples after wocDNA extraction for metabarcoding were sorted into specimens, which were individually DNA extracted, PCR amplified and tagged to sequence the full-length mtDNA COI barcode region (658bp) using Pacific BioSciences (PacBio) SMRT sequencing on a Sequel instrument (Hebert et al., 2018; Figure 1a). This resulted in the successful sequencing of 32,737 of the 36,402 sampled individuals (89.9%). For details, see Orsholm et al. (2025).

The taxonomic origin of barcode reference sequences was verified by their alignment against the NCBI-nt database (accessed November 2023; Sayers et al., 2018) using Kraken2 (Wood et al., 2019). Sequences classified as arthropods were retained using KrakenTools (Lu et al., 2022), retaining only sequences with a minimum overlap of 410bp with the 418bp fragment amplified for metabarcoding. This wide overlap between references and the metabarcoded fragment facilitates further classification of ASVs, where a 100% match between references and metabarcoded reads is required to classify ASVs as authentic (see Section 2.1.3). The reference sequence dataset was subsequently deduplicated to retain unique sequences, and sequences containing stop codons or shifts in the reading frame were manually removed, yielding a total of 6958 unique haplotypes. Sequence alignment, trimming, filtering by length and deduplication was performed with Geneious (Kearse et al., 2012).

2.1.3 | Metabarcoding

For each Malaise sample, a pool of individuals was extracted together. DNA extracts underwent a two-step PCR: the COI fragment was first amplified using primers BF3 and BR2, followed by a second PCR to attach P5/P7 Illumina adapters. The resulting amplicon

FIGURE 1 Overview of the denoising pipeline, where (a) describes the sampling and sequencing approach; (b) shows the pre-processing of sequencing reads to ASVs and classification of ASVs into verified authentic ASVs (vaASVs), verified non-authentic ASVs (vnaASVs) and unclassified ASVs (uASVs). (c) represents the general scheme of the denoising pipelines. The coloured steps, including LULU and clustering, are steps that are additionally added.

libraries were pooled and sequenced on a NovaSeq 6000 platform (paired-end; 2×250 bp; Modi et al., 2021). The 45 DNA pools were metabarcoded for the same 418 bp region of the COI gene used for vouchered specimens. Sequencing yielded approximately 364,500 raw reads per sample (median = 356,594; min = 156,640; max = 562,790; SD = 86,438). Full details on library preparation, tagging and sequencing are provided in de Waard et al. (2024).

2.2 | Metabarcoding data preparation for benchmarking pipeline

2.2.1 | Metabarcoding data pre-processing

Processing of raw metabarcoding reads before denoising was performed according to Andújar et al. (2022). First, raw reads were quality controlled with the tool fastQC (Andrews, 2010). Primers were then trimmed using cutadapt (Martin, 2011) and quality filtered using Trimmomatic with the parameters `-phred 33` and `Trailing:20` (Bolger et al., 2014). Reads were paired with fastq-pair (Edwards & Edwards, 2019) and merged in usearch using the option `-fastq_mergepairs` (Edgar, 2010). While the recommended approach for one of the denoisers (DADA2; Callahan et al., 2016) is to process paired-end reads separately, we merged them beforehand, facilitating direct comparison with other methods that use merged reads. This approach allows for a more consistent evaluation of different pipelines, enabling a comprehensive assessment of their performance in denoising and amplicon sequence variant (ASV) inference. Merged reads with a maximum expected error larger than 1 were discarded using usearch with `-fastq_maxee 1`, and library-level singletons (dereplicated unique sequences with only one read) were excluded. In addition, only merged reads that had an expected sequence length of 418 (+2 bp) were kept (`usearch -minseqlength 416 -maxseqlength 420`). Kraken2 (Wood et al., 2019) was used with the NCBI-nt database (accessed November 2023) to determine (non-)target taxa. Dereplicated unique sequences classified as arthropods were extracted using KrakenTools (Lu et al., 2022), which were then used as input for the denoising tools.

2.2.2 | Sequence classification

To maintain clarity in the workflow and facilitate pipeline comparisons, dereplicated unique sequences prior to denoising were designated as pre-processed ASVs and classified into three groups: verified authentic ASVs (vaASVs), verified non-authentic ASVs (vnaASVs) and unclassified ASVs (uASVs). This classification followed the

approach described in metaMATE (Andújar et al., 2021). Sequences were classified as vaASVs if they matched reference sequences with 100% similarity and had a minimum overlap of 410 bp using bbmap in `semiperfectmode` (Bushnell, 2014). Sequences were classified as vnaASVs if they contained a stop codon, insertion or deletion (indel) that changed the reading frame. All remaining sequences were classified as unclassified ASVs (uASVs).

2.3 | Benchmarking pipeline

The denoisers UNOISE3 (Edgar, 2016), DADA2 (Callahan et al., 2016) and DnoisE (Antich et al., 2021), along with the clustering tool SWARM (Mahé et al., 2014), were evaluated based on the survival of vaASVs and vnaASVs. Each method was tested with ten parameter settings to modulate filtering stringency, including both default and developer-recommended values, resulting in forty analyses overall. For each of these, denoising/clustering was followed by an additional step of chimera removal performed with usearch `-uchime3-denovo`. This tool has been designed to be used on denoised reads and results in a lower rate of false positive removal when compared to DADA2's `removeBimeraDenovo` algorithm (Edgar, 2016). In addition, the effect of secondary denoising with LULU (Frøslev et al., 2017), applied to the resulting denoised/clustering datasets, was evaluated (with LULU default parameters). Finally, denoised/clustering datasets, both with and without the use of LULU, were evaluated according to the survival of vaASVs and vnaASVs.

The eight datasets generated by applying the default parameters of UNOISE3, DADA2, DnoisE and SWARM—each with and without the additional processing step using LULU—were further analysed with metaMATE using two different filtering strategies and read abundance thresholds. This process resulted in 16 datasets in total, which were then used to create 2% similarity clusters to assess the impact of surviving vnaASVs on taxonomic inflation. A summary of these procedures is represented in Figure 1, and a detailed explanation of all analyses is provided below.

2.3.1 | Denoising pipelines

For comparative purposes, we use the pre-processed and dereplicated dataset with merged reads described above for all denoising tools, thus providing a comparable dataset across all denoisers. In general, denoising tools cluster unique sequences across all reads, where each cluster consists of a centroid sequence with high abundance and member sequences similar to the centroid but of lower abundance. It is assumed that the centroid is correct and that its

members are reads of the same template sequence with one or more errors. Unique features and comparison of the denoisers are provided in the subsequent sections.

DADA2

The core of DADA2 is its Divisive Amplicon Denoising Algorithm, which was built on a Poisson model of quality scores (a 4×4 transition matrix for each quality score). The core of DADA2 includes sequence comparison, filtering with quality scores/an error model and filtering by abundance thresholds (p -value) as the so-called divisive partitioning algorithm. Dereplicated sequences are placed into a single partition, and the most abundant sequence is placed as the centre of that partition. All sequences of the partition are then compared to the centre to calculate the error rates and the abundance p -value. Depending on the user-settable threshold of OMEGA_A, a new partition may be formed with the unique sequence corresponding to the lowest p -value placed as its centre. The centre of the new partition is then compared against all unique sequences. Other unique sequences can join the partition if they don't have p -values lower than OMEGA_A, in which case a new partition is created. This process is repeated until all abundance p -values are greater than OMEGA_A. The set of central sequences and the accompanying total abundances of those partitions then represent the inferred composition of the sample or, alternatively, each read is denoised by substituting the central sequence of its partition (Callahan et al., 2016). DADA2 v1.29.0 was used as an R package (<https://benjjneb.github.io/dada2/>) with OMEGA_A values ranging from $1e-100$ to $999e-3$. Later, when mentioning the DADA2 default, we refer to OMEGA_A equal to $1e-40$.

UNOISE3

UNOISE3 is part of the program usearch (<https://www.drive5.com/usearch/>; Edgar, 2016). In contrast to DADA2, UNOISE3 does not use quality scores and instead uses a one-pass clustering strategy with only two pre-set parameters.

Parameter α (default=2) controls how sensitive the UNOISE3 algorithm is to differences between sequences. A higher value of α means that more differences are permitted for a sequence to be considered a cluster member. This may be helpful when dealing with very noisy data, but it can also increase the chance of false positives. A lower value of α means that the algorithm is stricter and only identifies sequences as cluster members if they have very few differences with the cluster centroid. This can be helpful if the data is relatively clean, but it can also lead to false negatives. We executed UNOISE3 (v11.0.667) with different α values ranging from one to ten and with a `-minsize` of 2 to also exclude singletons. In this study, UNOISE3 default refers to `-minsize 2 -unoise_alpha 2`.

DnoisE

UNOISE3 does not consider that coding genes like COI have different levels of variability among codon positions, a feature which is absent in ribosomal genes. DnoisE seeks to improve the denoising performance of UNOISE3 by incorporating this information into the algorithm. Differentially weighting the d values (number of differences

between sequences) is suggested, according to the codon position where a difference occurs. This recognizes that third codon positions have the highest entropy (variability) followed by positions 1 and 2. Thus, the weighting scheme would assign more weight to differences in position 3 being real than to differences in position 2.

In the original UNOISE3 algorithm, a sequence is automatically assigned to the first centroid for which it satisfies the criteria. DnoisE instead stores all potential mothers for each sequence and allows for a more informed decision to be made about which mother to assign the sequence to. Antich et al. (2021) evaluated the performance of three algorithms: DnoisE, UNOISE3 and DADA2. Their focus was on improving denoising for coding genes (like COI) through entropy correction. However, a robust comparative assessment of the performance of all these methods remains to be undertaken. DnoisE v1.4.1 was installed using a dedicated conda environment as recommended on the authors' GitHub page. We executed DnoisE with different α values ranging from one to ten.

SWARM

SWARM is an amplicon-based single-linkage clustering tool. It uses k -mer filtering to reduce the number of comparisons required and exact global pairwise alignment for high clustering accuracy. SWARM also includes a post-processing step to break up chains of amplicons that can potentially link closely related dereplicated unique sequences and decrease clustering resolution. The parameter d is the distance to use as the local clustering threshold. In order to maximize the yield of biological information and produce the best partition of the amplicon space, d is set to 1 by default (Mahé et al., 2021). Parameter d is suggested to have a smaller effect on clustering results than adjustments in other clustering tools, and Mahé et al. (2014) recommend a d value of 1, 2 or 3. SWARM v 3.1.5 was executed with the source code provided (<https://github.com/torognes/swarm>) using d values between 1 and 10.

2.3.2 | Post-denoising filtering with LULU and metaMATE

LULU

LULU is a post-clustering or post-denoising curation approach that aims to detect and eliminate incorrect OTUs (or ASVs) from tables generated by any clustering/denoising algorithm. LULU's algorithm is predicated on the idea that many OTUs in OTU tables are actually methodological and/or analytical errors or rare (intra-genomic) variants. LULU operates by iteratively traversing the OTU table and identifying potential erroneous OTUs based on co-occurrence patterns and centroid sequence pairwise similarity. After identifying these extra OTUs, they can be merged with their parent OTUs to maintain the total read count while reducing the OTU count to yield what is suggested to be more realistic compared to applying a simple clustering threshold (97%) after denoising (Frøsvlev et al., 2017). We evaluated LULU in combination with all denoising and clustering tools using its default settings.

metaMATE

Dereplicated unique sequences (without denoising), together with datasets generated using default parameters of UNOISE3, DADA2, DnoisE and SWARM—with and without additional processing by LULU—were analysed using metaMATE (Andújar et al., 2021: <https://github.com/tjcreedy/metamate>; v0.4.0). For each metaMATE analysis, the input ASV abundance table by library was generated using `vsearch -search_exact`.

MetaMATE was executed in the 'find' mode to explore the performance of different filtering strategies and abundance thresholds on the percentage of surviving authentic and non-authentic ASVs. More specifically, we filtered by: (a) the total read count per ASV across samples, with thresholds ranging from 1 to 250; (b) the total read count per ASV per sample, with thresholds ranging from 1 to 100; (c) the percentage of reads that belong to an ASV across samples, with 200 thresholds ranging from 0.00001 to 0.01; (d) the percentage of reads that belong to an ASV per sample, with 300 thresholds ranging from 0.00001 to 0.01; and (e) the combination of *d* and the percentage of reads by clade with 100 thresholds from 0.0001 to 0.5. Clades were defined as groups of closely related ASVs with a similarity threshold of 80% based on pairwise sequence distances. Both the pipeline with no denoising and DnoisE without LULU yielded input datasets for UPGMA tree construction in metaMATE that exceeded the maximum allowed number of ASVs ($n=65,536$), so the filtering strategy using clades (e) was not performed.

In addition to providing both the number and percentage of surviving vnaASVs and vaASVs, metaMATE also estimates the total number of authentic and non-authentic ASVs in the resulting metaMATE-filtered dataset, based on the observed survival rates of vaASVs and vnaASVs. The accuracy of these estimates depends on the assumption that the verified ASVs (vaASV and vnaASVs) are representative of the entire populations of aASVs and naASVs, respectively. Across all abundance-based filtering in metaMATE, two representative output datasets were retained: (i) the dataset with the highest number of ASVs where the estimated percentage of naASVs was below 5%; (ii) the dataset with the highest number of ASVs with a percentage of surviving vnaASVs below 5%. These estimates were calculated without the fine-tuning performed in the 'dump' mode of metaMATE, where vaASVs previously filtered out are re-included and surviving vnaASVs are excluded from the final output dataset.

2.3.3 | Clustering and evaluation of OTUs

The effect of the alternative denoising and filtering pipelines on the recovery of species was also assessed by clustering the resulting ASVs to form Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) that approximate species-level groupings. While such OTUs do not definitively represent species, they can serve as a useful alternative. We defined OTUs using a 2% dissimilarity threshold, to roughly approach the threshold that is often applied in BOLD systems for species-level identification and to define BINs (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2013). While the BIN

approach is more flexible (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2013), this 2% value remains a good proxy for the purpose of exploring OTU inflation and comparing among pipelines. OTUs were classified into three categories: (i) OTUs that contain at least one verified authentic ASV (vaASVs) were designated as verified authentic OTUs (vaOTUs); (ii) OTUs exclusively containing verified non-authentic ASVs (vnaASVs) were classified as verified non-authentic OTUs (vnaOTUs); and (iii) OTUs comprising a combination of vnaASVs and unclassified ASVs were categorized as unclassified OTUs (uOTUs). OTU clusters at 2% were defined with `hclust` (R package Stats) on the UPGMA tree generated using the `dist.dna` function (R package ape; Paradis & Schliep, 2018) and the UPGMA function (R package phangorn; Schliep, 2010). The number of dereplicated unique sequences (without denoising), as well as ASVs after DnoisE with default parameters and without LULU, exceeded the maximum number of input sequences for `dist.dna`. To circumvent this, the dereplicated unique sequences or ASVs were first clustered within 10% dissimilarity groups using Geneious, and the 2% threshold was applied as above for each of these groups.

2.4 | Visualization and hardware

Visualization of the results was primarily done with R (Wickham, 2016) and the R package ggplot2 (R Development Core Team, 2020). Adjustments of the y-axis scales were undertaken with the R package ggbreak (Xu et al., 2021), and Venn Diagrams were generated with the R package VennDiagram (Chen & Boutros, 2011). Data analyses were performed on a computer running Ubuntu 22.04 LTE with an i9-10900X processor (20 cores; 3.70 GHz) and 64 GB RAM.

3 | RESULTS

Processing of metabarcode data prior to denoising resulted in a total of 1,748,291 unique sequences across all samples. The majority of unique sequences were singletons (1,426,595 sequences; 81.6%) and were excluded from further analyses. Subsequently, 985 unique sequences classified as non-arthropod were additionally excluded. The final dataset used for benchmarking denoising pipelines included 320,711 unique sequences. Of these, 4485 sequences matched with 100% similarity to one of the 6958 barcode reference sequences and were classified as vaASVs. The number of vnaASVs was approximately threefold that of vaASVs, with 14,773 sequences (vna-)ASVs containing stop codons or frameshift mutations. The remaining 301,453 sequences were classified as uASVs.

3.1 | Primary denoising and parameter settings

Comparing the total ASV count across the primary denoisers and different parameter settings revealed extensive variation in the number

of surviving ASVs. DnoisE exhibited the highest number of surviving ASVs (default settings: 108,981 ASVs; across the range of parameter settings: 21,247–149,636 ASVs). DADA2 displayed the most consistent performance under different parameter settings, with a marked increase in ASVs only at the highest OMEGA_A values (default settings: 10,079 ASVs; across the range of parameter settings: 6,635–35,956 ASVs). UNOISE3 presented the greatest sensitivity to α settings, with greater variation in total ASVs compared to the other primary denoisers (default settings: 23,506 ASVs; across the range of parameter settings: 16,935–217,237 ASVs). Finally, SWARM produced 45,830 ASVs with the default settings ($d=1$), with an ASV count ranging from 15,567 to 45,830 across the range of parameter settings evaluated.

The total number of surviving vaASVs ranged from 2908 (SWARM; $d=10$) to 4412 (UNOISE3; $\alpha=10$) across primary denoising tools and parameter settings. In contrast, the number of retained vnaASVs differed greatly, with a minimum of 174 (DADA2; OMEGA_A=1e-100) and a maximum of 5504 (UNOISE3; $\alpha=10$). UNOISE3 displayed a dramatic increase in vnaASVs with higher α values, whereas DnoisE consistently retained a low number of vnaASVs despite an increase in the total number of surviving ASVs with increasing α values. DADA2 produced an increase in vnaASVs only with the most relaxed OMEGA_A settings. SWARM exhibited a high number of vnaASVs for the default settings. All denoising pipelines maximized the ratio of surviving vaASVs to vnaASVs with the strictest parameter settings (Figure 2). In terms of the ratio of vaASVs to the total number of surviving ASVs, as well as the (lowest) number of vnaASVs, DADA2 performed best.

Comparison of surviving ASVs across all primary denoisers and SWARM (under default settings) reveals 7361 ASVs that are shared across all four tools. UNOISE3 and DADA2 present a limited number

of unique ASVs, with 2984 and 44 respectively. In stark contrast, DnoisE and SWARM yielded 76,335 and 17,554 unique ASVs respectively, highlighting a substantial influence of the denoising tool selected on the landscape of ASVs recovered (Figure 3a).

3.2 | LULU

Secondary denoising with LULU (default parameters) dramatically reduced the total number of ASVs across all denoising pipelines. The lowest number of ASVs ($n=3787$) was generated together with primary denoising using DADA2 (OMEGA_A=1e-100), whereas the highest number ($n=8241$) obtained was together with UNOISE3 ($\alpha=7$). LULU reduced the number of surviving vaASVs by approximately 1000 for each pipeline. Parameter setting for each denoising tool showed little impact on the number of retained vaASVs after applying LULU. The retained number of vnaASVs followed the same pattern, where parameter settings for each denoising tool had little impact on the reduction (Figure 4). Secondary denoising with LULU led to a substantial reduction of surviving ASVs unique to one method, with a maximum of 2227 for SWARM, followed by UNOISE3 with 1441, DnoisE with 1350 and DADA2 with 9 (Figure 3b).

3.3 | metaMATE

MetaMATE filtering resulted in a consistent trend: with increasing threshold stringency, larger proportions of vnaASVs were removed. Additionally, more stringent filtering criteria resulted in a greater reduction of vnaASVs compared to vaASVs across all pipelines, resulting in increases in the estimated ratio of aASVs to naASVs. In general,

FIGURE 2 Number of vaASVs, vnaASVs and total number of ASVs (y-axis) obtained by denoising with DADA2, UNOISE3, DnoisE and SWARM with decreasing stringency (x-axis). (a–d) Number of vaASVs (green line, squares), vnaASVs (red line, triangles). (e–h) Total number of ASVs (black line, dots). The vertical dashed line represents the default stringency of each denoising tool.

FIGURE 3 Venn diagram displaying the overlap of amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) after different denoising strategies (UNOISE3, DnoisE, DADA2, SWARM) using default parameters without additional filtering (a) and processed with LULU (b).

FIGURE 4 Number of vaASVs, vnaASVs and total number of ASVs (y-axis) obtained by denoising with DADA2, UNOISE3, DnoisE and SWARM with decreasing stringency (x-axis) and after post-processing with LULU. (a–d) Number of vaASVs (green line, squares), vnaASVs (red line, triangles). (e–h) Total number of ASVs (black line, dots). The vertical dashed line represents the default stringency of each denoising tool.

DADA2 consistently required a stricter threshold to eliminate 95% of vnaASVs compared to UNOISE3 and DnoisE. Notably, DADA2 also removed a lower proportion of vaASVs at higher thresholds compared to the other primary denoisers (Figure 5).

MetaMATE filtering for the survival of no more than 5% of estimated naASVs (strict filter) dramatically reduced the total number of ASVs in all denoising pipelines (970–3347 ASVs retained from a

total of 10,079–108,981). The number of retained unclassified ASVs ranged from 123 with SWARM and LULU to 1653 with DnoisE, which represents a reduction of 97.5% and 98.4%, respectively. The number of vaASVs ranged from 791 for the pipeline without primary denoising (17.6% surviving) and up to 2108 with UNOISE3 (54% surviving). The estimated number of retained naASVs is below 10 for all denoising pipelines, and the number of retained estimated aASVs

FIGURE 5 Results on the survival of ASVs (y-axis) after the implementation of metaMATE on the ASVs datasets obtained from DADA2, UNOISE3, DnoisE and SWARM & LULU pipelines with increasing minimum absolute ASV abundance filtering by library (x-axis). (a–d) Proportion of non-retained vaASVs (green) and retained vnaASVs (red) after metaMATE filtering. (e–h): Estimations obtained with metaMATE of the number of aASVs (green shade) and naASVs (red shade) in the initial denoised datasets used as metaMATE inputs and in the output ASV datasets after abundance filtering with metaMATE (lines).

ranged between 983 for SWARM with LULU (36.2% surviving) and 3196 for DnoisE (74.4% surviving; [Figure 6](#)). No primary denoising resulted in the lowest number of estimated aASVs across all pipelines, with 927 (20.7% surviving).

The relaxed filter with metaMATE, where less than 5% of vnaASVs are kept, typically resulted in higher numbers of surviving ASVs when compared with the strict filter. Here, the only exception was DADA2 in combination with LULU, where slightly more ASVs were retained using the strict filter. Relaxed filtering resulted in more surviving vnaASVs compared to the strict filter (e.g. 50.2% and 63.9% for DADA2 and 54.1% compared to 73.3% for UNOISE3), but also retained substantially more vnaASVs. The lowest number of surviving vnaASVs was achieved with the pipeline DnoisE in combination with LULU ($n=1$), and the highest number of surviving vnaASVs was obtained without primary denoising ($n=670$), followed by UNOISE3 ($n=41$). The reduction in the maximum proportion of surviving ASVs unique to a pipeline was higher for metaMATE (2.9%–10.2%) than for LULU (0.22%–28.3%). This greater efficiency of metaMATE at removing spurious ASVs is, however, accompanied by a lower number of ASVs shared across all pipelines compared to LULU (2761 vs. 3296, [Figure 7a](#)). When both metaMATE and LULU are jointly used, the difference across the four primary denoisers is minimized. However, this also reduced the number of shared ASVs even more to 2195.

3.4 | Clustering and evaluation of OTUs

Clustering with a 98% cut-off of the dereplicated unique sequences (pre-processed ASVs; $n=320,711$) resulted in 15,558 OTUs. Of these, 2327 contained at least one vaASV and were classified as vaOTUs; 287 were exclusively formed by vnaASVs and were classified as vnaOTUs; the remaining 12,944 were classified as uOTUs. To serve as a reference for the number of authentic OTUs, we also clustered the set of 6958 barcode reference sequences, which resulted in 3451 OTUs ([Figure 8](#)).

Denosing with DADA2, UNOISE3 and DnoisE returned quite similar numbers of vaOTUs: 2216, 2268 and 2449 respectively. In contrast, only 1743 vaOTUs were obtained with SWARM. The number of vnaOTUs ranged between 94 with DnoisE and 267 with UNOISE3 (or 287 without primary denoising). However, DnoisE showed the highest number of uOTUs after primary denoising ($n=9665$; ranging from 4199 to 9665). Secondary denoising with LULU reduced the number of vaOTUs to 1929 (87.1%), 2013 (88.8%) and 2118 (86.5%) together with DADA2, UNOISE3 and DnoisE respectively. In contrast, the combination of SWARM with LULU yielded a higher number of vaOTUs ($n=2009$) compared to SWARM alone. Similarly, the number of vnaOTUs was reduced to a minimum of 23 with DnoisE and a maximum of 97 with SWARM.

FIGURE 6 Overview of the denoising pipelines (no denoising, DADA2, UNOISE3, DnoisE, SWARM) depicted by the total amount of amplicon sequence variants (ASVs), verified authentic ASVs (vaASVs) and verified non-authentic ASVs (vnaASVs). The output of each primary denoising tool was additionally processed with LULU. The number of retained ASVs after abundance filtering ($<5\%$ estimated number of non-authentic ASVs) with metaMATE is indicated together with the estimated number of authentic ASVs (aASVs; green striped bar) and the number of estimated non-authentic ASVs (naASVs; red striped bar). (D) Numbers of vaASVs, vnaASVs and unclassified ASVs after denoising. (D + M) retained numbers and proportions of vaASVs, vnaASVs and unclassified ASVs after processing of output from (D) with metaMATE. (D + M est) Estimated numbers and proportions of authentic ASVs and non-authentic ASVs resulting from processing of output from (D) with metaMATE. (D + M r) relaxed filtering with metaMATE where less than $<5\%$ vnaASVs were retained. (D + M s) strict metaMATE filtering where less than $<5\%$ estimated naASVs were retained.

In general, large numbers of ASVs were assigned to unclassified OTUs if no additional abundance filtering (with metaMATE) was applied. For example, DADA2 without secondary denoising

with metaMATE yielded more unclassified OTUs ($n=4199$) than authentic OTUs (vaOTUs; $n=2216$), whereas with strict metaMATE filtering, the number of uOTUs was reduced to 282 and the

FIGURE 7 Venn diagram displaying the overlap of amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) after metaMATE using different denoising strategies (UNOISE3, DnoisE, DADA2, SWARM) with default parameters (a) and processed with LULU (b). In both cases, additional abundance filtering with metaMATE was applied, where less than 5% estimated non-authentic ASVs were kept.

number of vaOTUs to 1265. The different filtering strategies applied in metaMATE resulted in a similar number of vaOTUs surviving for DADA2 ($n=1265$) and UNOISE3 ($n=1347$). For DnoisE and SWARM, the differences between filtering strategies are much more evident, where, for example the number of vaOTUs was almost doubled with the relaxed filtering (1725 and 1922) compared to the strict filtering (974 and 1020). With the strict filtering, the number of vnaOTUs ranged between 0 and 4, whereas for the relaxed filtering, up to 51 vnaOTUs survived (with SWARM). With the exception of DADA2, the combination with LULU resulted in slight reductions in the total number of surviving OTUs after metaMATE was applied (Figure 8).

4 | DISCUSSION

Our analyses have demonstrated that the effectiveness of denoising metabarcode data largely depends on secondary filtering or clustering steps applied after a primary denoising tool. Results obtained from a primary denoising tool alone are not reliable. LULU, as a secondary denoiser, removed large proportions of unclassified ASVs and verified non-authentic sequences, but this came at the cost of also removing approximately 25% of authentic sequences. Secondary denoising with metaMATE produced the most favourable results in the context of the overall proportion of retained sequences that are authentic. However, similar to LULU, this came with a collateral cost of the loss of a similar proportion of authentic sequences. Clustering ASVs to OTUs with a 98% similarity threshold after

primary denoising resulted in non-trivial overestimation of OTUs, revealing many unclassified ASVs to be very divergent from authentic ASVs. Thus, we do not recommend clustering of sequences to OTUs after primary denoising as an approach to reduce noise. However, clustering after secondary denoising greatly reduces the influence of OTUs that are not representative of target species.

4.1 | Performance of denoising tools

UNOISE3, DnoisE, DADA2 and SWARM are all capable of recovering respectable proportions of authentic ASVs (from 75.1%–95.8%). However, this is compromised by the retention of large numbers of non-authentic and unclassified ASVs. In the case of unclassified ASVs, they accounted for 61% of all denoised sequences in the case of DADA2 and up to 95.4% in the case of DnoisE. While it is almost certain that some of these unclassified ASVs were authentic, our experimental design demonstrates that the great majority are, in fact, non-authentic. A sequencing success rate of 89.7% across the 36,402 individuals sampled from the 45 Malaise traps yielded sequences for 32,737 individuals, resulting in 6958 unique sequences. Of the 6958 unique sequences, 5030 (72.3%) were present in the metabarcoding reads before denoising. Based on this, and assuming similar proportions, it can be inferred that approximately 795 additional unique sequences could be anticipated from the 3743 unsequenced individuals. Additionally, it is reasonable to expect that a similar proportion of these sequences (32,737 out of 36,402 individuals; 10.1%) might fail to amplify and sequence in metabarcoding, with another

FIGURE 8 Overview of the barcode reference sequences and denoising pipelines (DADA2, UNOISE3, DnoisE, SWARM and LULU) depicted by the total number of operational taxonomic units (OTUs). OTUs were classified as being an authentic OTU (aOTU) if at least one ASV in the OTU is a verified authentic ASV (vaASV), as a non-authentic OTU (naOTU) if the OTU consists uniquely of verified non-authentic ASVs and otherwise as an unclassified OTU (uOTU). LULU was applied to the output of each denoising tool. The number of retained OTUs was obtained after abundance filtering ($* < 5\%$ non-authentic OTUs) with metaMATE. (D) Numbers of vaOTUs and unclassified (including vna-) OTUs after denoising. (D+M) retained numbers of vaOTUs and unclassified (including vna-) OTUs after processing the output from (D) with metaMATE. (D+M r) relaxed filtering with metaMATE where less than $< 5\%$ vnaASVs were retained. (D+M s) strict metaMATE filtering where less than $< 5\%$ estimated naASVs were retained.

10.8% (4485 out of 5030 vaASVs) likely excluded as singletons or non-arthropods. These projections suggest that the true number of authentic ASVs is approximately 5657, and thus that only 627 of the unclassified ASVs are, in fact, authentic. Across all denoisers, the number of unclassified ASVs vastly exceeds this value, highlighting non-authentic ASVs as a pervasive and dominant feature of their

output (Figure 6). Accounting for the potential occurrence of 627 authentic ASVs and removing them from the total number of unclassified ASVs yields total counts of 5526, 18,010, 103,385 and 38,963 remaining unclassified ASVs for DADA2, UNOISE3, DnoisE and SWARM respectively. These ASVs are expected to represent a combination of PCR errors, sequencing errors, NUMTs, potential

contaminant sequences and secondary amplifications (endosymbionts, parasitoids, prey items, etc).

4.2 | Parameter settings and their impact

The primary denoisers executed with default values retained numbers of ASVs that vastly exceed the estimated number of haplotypes: 1.8x expected ASV count with DADA2, 4.2x with UNOISE3, 8.1x with SWARM and 19.3x with DnoisE. For all denoisers, stricter parameter settings removed higher proportions of non-authentic ASVs compared to authentic ones (Figure 2). As the number of retained authentic sequences only decreases slightly with stricter parameter settings, we conclude more stringent settings will be preferable in many cases.

Antich et al. (2021) compared the effects of different parameter settings with DADA2 and UNOISE3. However, their results cannot be directly compared with ours, as they focused on entropy levels rather than the resulting number of ASVs. With their comparison, they laid the groundwork for DnoisE, which is based on the algorithm of UNOISE3. One of the biggest changes Antich et al. (2021) made for DnoisE compared to UNOISE3 is a more relaxed filtering stringency to optimize entropy, with a default α parameter of five instead of two. The relatively low proportion of vnaASVs recovered with DnoisE indicates that its entropy-based filtering strategy is effective in the removal of NUMTs with either indels or stop codons. However, the comparatively large number of retained uASVs compared to DADA2 and UNOISE3 reveals that erroneous sequences and NUMTs closely resembling functional mitochondrial COI sequences are less effectively removed. In comparison with the other primary denoisers, DnoisE presented an extremely high number of ASVs with default settings, but retained a similar number of ASVs to UNOISE3 when more stringent α values were applied. It is noteworthy that Antich et al. (2021) suggest denoising tools be used together with clustering tools. Thus, DnoisE may not have been designed as a tool for denoising without further processing steps.

4.3 | LULU

Secondary denoising with LULU proved to efficiently remove vnaASVs and results were broadly similar irrespective of (i) the parameter settings used for primary denoising and (ii) the primary denoiser used (Figure 3b, Figure 4). Application of LULU increased the consistency of results across different primary denoisers, and substantially reduced the number of vnaASVs and uASVs. Nonetheless, it came at the cost of removing approximately 25% of authentic ASVs.

4.4 | metaMATE

Relaxed metaMATE filtering to keep $\leq 5\%$ of vnaASVs showed greater variability across different primary denoisers than strict filtering,

where $\leq 5\%$ of estimated naASVs are retained. This supports the filtering recommendation of Andújar et al. (2021) to retain $\leq 5\%$ of estimated naASVs. This filtering approach, together with each of the primary denoisers evaluated here, resulted in proportions of retained vnaASVs that approached zero. When applying strict metaMATE filtering, unclassified ASVs underwent approximately 10-fold, 30-fold, 60-fold and 120-fold reductions for DADA2, UNOISE3, DnoisE and SWARM respectively, with the final number of unclassified ASVs for all but DnoisE falling within expectations for the additional 627 authentic ASVs here lacking reference sequences (Figure 6). While metaMATE outperformed LULU with regard to the proportion of unclassified ASVs removed, it also resulted in more vaASVs being removed than were removed with LULU. The combination of LULU together with metaMATE did not lead to improvement.

Applying metaMATE with subsequent clustering might require further refinement of the filtering strategy. We tested two approaches: a relaxed strategy (retaining $\leq 5\%$ of vnaASVs) and a strict strategy (retaining $\leq 5\%$ of estimated naASVs). The relaxed approach yielded 1475–2918 OTUs, which were a closer match to the 3451 OTUs expected from barcode references. In contrast, the strict strategy drastically reduced the OTU count, retaining only 6%–49% of the expected number.

4.5 | Clustering ASVs into OTUs

Clustering ASVs into OTUs with a 98% similarity threshold grouped some unclassified ASVs together with authentic ASVs, and as such, they do not contribute to inflated OTU diversity estimates (Figures 6 and 8). Across all combinations of primary and secondary denoisers, the numbers of ASVs that cluster within vaOTUs were typically high. This reveals that a substantial proportion of unclassified ASVs and vnaASVs are more consequential for the inflation of genetic variation within species than is the inflation of species number itself. Nevertheless, OTU/species inflation continued to be a substantial problem, which is reflected by the presence of vnaOTUs and a high number of uOTUs. Thus, our findings are consistent with those of Arjona et al. (2022), who describe extensive taxonomic inflation from non-target sequences assigned to novel OTUs after denoising. Creedy et al. (2018) also found high levels of OTU inflation after denoising with UNOISE3 and subsequent clustering. They proposed several potential, but not mutually exclusive causes: systemic disparities in molecular species divergences, difficulty of accurately distinguishing between similar-looking species during sample sorting and the presence of NUMTs. Ingested animals further contribute to this uncertainty in metabarcoding studies by introducing their own mitochondrial DNA and potentially their own NUMTs into the sample, making it challenging to distinguish between target species, prey species and contamination. While accounting for the exact contribution of NUMTs to the observed noise is challenging, several recent studies have proposed NUMTs as a main source of taxonomic inflation (Arjona et al., 2022; Schultz & Hebert, 2022). Creedy et al. (2018) concluded that OTU inflation was consistently biased to

a similar extent across independent samples. Thus, while absolute numbers of OTUs may be unreliable, comparative analyses could be deployed. Our analyses provide a more nuanced understanding of this inflation and how it can be dealt with or accommodated.

4.6 | Implications and recommendations for metabarcoding

This study has three important implications for metabarcoding. First, we have demonstrated how primary denoising, independent of the parameter settings, is not enough to efficiently remove concomitant sequences (naASVs) generated with metabarcoding, as has also been reported in previous studies (Andújar et al., 2021; Arjona et al., 2022; Elbrecht et al., 2018). Second, our results also demonstrate that secondary denoising/filtering with tools such as metaMATE and LULU can greatly improve the removal of undesirable concomitant sequences, but at the cost of some data loss. Third, we demonstrate that the recommendation to generate OTUs by clustering after a single round of denoising (Antich et al., 2021) is not adequate, as it still generates approximately 100% to 250% OTU-level taxonomic inflation in our dataset, which is in agreement with inflated OTU numbers reported in previous studies (Creedy et al., 2018; Frøslev et al., 2017). We instead recommend that clustering should be optionally deployed either before or after secondary denoising.

The most promising pipeline for denoising was determined to be primary denoising with UNOISE3 or DADA2 in combination with LULU or metaMATE as secondary denoisers. These combinations resulted in high levels of vaASV retention, with little to no surviving vnaASVs, generating a number of unclassified ASVs that fell in the range of additionally expected aASVs. Particularly useful is the implementation of metaMATE, which allows the selection of filtering stringency for the final proportion of naASVs expected to occur in the filtered dataset. The more stringent secondary denoising consistently comes at the cost of a significant loss in the recovery of authentic sequences (aASVs), a trade-off already described by Andújar et al. (2021). In our controlled metabarcoding experiment, with references available for 32,737 of the 36,402 specimens forming our communities, a non-trivial number of barcode reference sequences were represented by very low-frequency ASVs. This is exemplified by 545 singletons (sequences detected by only one read) that match to a barcode reference sequence. Although these represent only 0.04% of all singletons in our dataset, they also represent 11% of all metabarcoding sequences matching to a reference sequence. Most denoising tools remove singletons by default—and in the case of UNOISE3, even ASVs comprised of up to seven copies (Edgar, 2025). This illustrates how any denoising pipeline can imply a notable loss of authentic ASVs. Noise generated by PCR and sequencing errors, as well as the co-amplification of NUMTs, is expected to generate low abundance variants when compared to authentic mitochondrial sequences of the same organism. However, our results illustrate a substantial abundance overlap between naASVs and aASVs that complicates denoising.

There are now a myriad of options available for the bioinformatic processing of metabarcoding data, each with the common objective of producing sequence alignments that both (i) remove all variation that is not strictly of mitochondrial origin and (ii) maximize the information content relative to the biological sample that underpins the sequencing itself. Here we have revealed this to be a complex task, the challenges of which many researchers are likely to have been fully unaware of. We have also demonstrated that secondary denoising should be employed as a fundamental step to mitigate this problem. While using primary and secondary denoisers together may complicate the implementation of metabarcoding pipelines, the recent development of automated metabarcoding workflows with graphical user interfaces (GUI) allows for the integration of primary (DADA2 and UNOISE3) and secondary (LULU and metaMATE) denoisers. One example of such a GUI is PipeCraft2 (Anslan et al., 2017; <https://pipecraft2-manual.readthedocs.io>), which offers the opportunity for a more informed and reproducible cleaning of metabarcoding data.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conception or design of the work: Carmelo Andújar, Brent C. Emerson, Marius Hannes Eisele. Acquiring of funds: Brent C. Emerson, Carmelo Andújar. Data generation: Tomas Roslin, Otso Ovaskainen, Brendan Furneaux. Data analysis: Marius Hannes Eisele, Carmelo Andújar. Manuscript preparation: Marius Hannes Eisele, Brent C. Emerson, Carmelo Andújar. Review and edition of manuscript: Marius Hannes Eisele, Brent C. Emerson, Carmelo Andújar, Brendan Furneaux, Tomas Roslin, Otso Ovaskainen.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest associated with this work. The research was conducted independently and without any financial, commercial or personal relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict.

PEER REVIEW

The peer review history for this article is available at <https://www.webofscience.com/api/gateway/wos/peer-review/10.1111/2041-210x.70159>.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Raw sequences have been shared on ENA under the project accession number PRJEB86111 and barcode sequences are available on BOLD with the project ID DS-LPEPA22 (Orsholm et al., 2025). R and BASH scripts used in this study are deposited in the open-source database Zenodo via <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14762522> (Eisele et al., 2025).

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